

ADOLESCENT AUTONOMY

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Annotation: this article highlights the adolescent autonomy status observed in adolescence, the types of adolescent autonomy such as legal autonomy, emotional autonomy, spatial autonomy. Feedback has also been provided on the characteristics of the manifestation of feelings of loneliness in adolescents.

Keywords: adolescence, autonomy, legal autonomy, emotional autonomy, spatial autonomy.

Adolescence includes periods from 11-12 years, to 14-15 years. In most students, the transition to adolescence begins mainly in the 5th grade. "No longer a teenage child, but not a big one"- the same definition indicates an important character of adolescence. Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, characterized by physiological and psychological physical characteristics. At this stage, the physical and psychic development of children is greatly accelerated, interest in various things in life, desire for novelty increases, character is formed, the spiritual world is enriched, conflicts are escalated. Adolescence is a period of puberty and is also characterized by the emergence of new sensations, sensations and confused issues related to sexual life. Influenced by these, the character of the teenager, his treatment of people around him, his attitude to what is happening in society are rapidly changing. Sometimes, due to the formation of false tassavur and erroneous opinions about social issues, he looks with a critical eye at certain order rules.

Adolescence is a period Rich in contradictions. From the age of 11-12, the teenager begins to think logically. In his psyche, such crisis situations occur in which he solves this crisis on the one hand, and from the other side, he does not have the opportunity, strength and intelligence to solve it on his own.

One of the characteristic features of adolescence is the state of adolescent autonomy, which is observed in adolescents during this period. Such types of adolescent

autonomy as legal autonomy, emotional autonomy, spatial autonomy are distinguished.

It is known that the child will need someone's care from the day of birth. His parents and other loved ones feed him, dress him, raise him and keep the child under regular supervision. They support the child in every possible way, and the child feels the need for such support, encouragement. In adolescence, however, the child gains relative independence in ensuring his or her life, safety. Now he will be able to protect himself, if necessary, to work at the level of his capabilities, make sufficient income, independently satisfy his needs.

The legal autonomy mentioned above is characterized by the fact that at the same time the child reaches adolescence, giving him a number of legal opportunities. During this period, the child will be considered a legal entity and will have the right to vote. While Mabodo's teenage parents are separated during this period, in this case, where and with whom the teenager remains is decided according to the wishes of the child. Sometimes, as a result of parents' lack of freedom for the adolescent, they become anti-parental. It should be noted that on the basis of this communication and attitude, the feeling of pride in adolescents also begins to form. It is also possible for the child to formally engage in physical labor during this period, based on his own opportunity. If necessary, they will also be required to respond to their behavior, actions. Having similar legal opportunities and from this the awareness of the teenager ensures the emergence of his legal autonomy. Having such autonomy creates a sense of responsibility, responsibility for one's behavior in a teenager.

Another of the adolescent autonomies is emotional autonomy. It is known that from the moment the child comes into the world, he feels the need for emotional, emotional support, Trust, show affection, caress of his mother and those around him. That is why, when children of early childhood, preschool and junior school age are shown emotional closeness to them by leaning, caressing them, stroking them on the head and saying pleasant things and treats, they rejoice, rejoice in it and despise the person being caressed. We can observe this in the case when young children lean on their mother, they are sucked into the Pinyin, they are pampered. Also, when children are in conflict in their interactions with their peers, and especially when they "suffer" from their peers, "begin to be overcome", expect emotional encouragement, emotional clairvoyance from their parents and their loved ones around them and turn to them in this regard. If he can receive this emotional encouragement in time, he will feel free, refreshed, victorious and rejoice with them. The little one feels the

need for adult help in solving the "problems" he faced in his life, seeks to use them regularly. Adults are friendly with adolescents, adolescents look positively, but if this leadership is at the forefront of the desire of an adult, then they are completely opposed. This resistance can often lead to negative results, sometimes a state of depression. This condition often occurs in the families of adolescents whose parents have an authoritarian attitude. It will be a while difficult for adolescents raised in such families to carry out their own plans to act independently in life, to take on a difficult upbringing.

Another state of autonomy observed in adolescents is spatial autonomy. According to this, adolescents strive to be alone in their room as much as possible, to be as lonely as possible when they are doing something or somewhere, especially to be in the chatrok from the point of view of their parents, family members, to spend time obsessed with their own fantasies. Even though they talk mostly their peers, close comrades remain preoccupied with themselves, seeking to communicate as little as possible with their parents as they know. At the same time, some parents who do not understand the true cause of these phenomena observed in a teenager are envied by their state of affairs and become more interested in them than before. In other words they "invade" their autonomy. And teenagers don't like it. Such situations can be the basis for disagreements, conflicts in the interaction between adolescents and their parents.

When communicating with a teenager, parents must first communicate and react, taking into account that the teenager is in a period of physical, psychological transition. Although the process of sexual development has an indirect effect on the teenager, not directly, it is during these periods that various changes occur in the child's psyche. It is also of course desirable if teachers treat it based on their psychological character-characteristics, attaching special importance to it.

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